

Synthesis of complexes of *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-thiocarbamide with some bivalent transition metal ions

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A series of binuclear complexes of types $[M_2(BPT)_2(H_2O)_4]$ and $[M_2(BPT)_2L_4]$, where $H_2BPT = N$ -benzoyl-*N'*-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-thiocarbamide, $L =$ pyridine or picolines (α, β, γ), $M = Cu^{II}$, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} have been synthesized. The ligand acts as a tridentate dibasic donor coordinating through carbonyl oxygen, thiocarbamido sulfur and deprotonated phenolic oxygen to yield the metal complexes in which water is replaceable by pyridine or picolines.

The magnetic and electronic spectral data indicate the complexes to be in an approximately octahedral environment, the symmetry being O_h for the Co^{II} and D_{4h} for others. Crystal field parameters for the Co^{II} and distortion parameters for the Ni^{II} complexes on the basis of proposed geometry have been calculated.

As a part of our continuing research on the study of metal complexes with bioactive ligands containing NOS donor groups¹, we report here synthetic and structural studies on the complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with the ligand *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-(2-hydroxyphenyl)thiocarbamide (H_2BPT).

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are insoluble in water and most of the common organic solvents, but slightly soluble in dioxane and DMF. Low molar conductance values in DMSO (5.2 – $6.8 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) indicate their non-electrolytic nature.

IR spectrum of the ligand shows bands at $\sim 3350 cm^{-1}$ (hydrogen bonded OH of phenolic group)², ~ 3320 (NH of C_6H_5NH) and $3100 cm^{-1}$ ($C_6H_5-CO-NH-CS$). Presence of the ligand in thione and keto form is inferred by the appearance of bands at ~ 1640 , 1550 , 1380 , 1180 and $840 cm^{-1}$ due to $\nu_{C=O}$ and thioamide bands, respectively, and the absence of ν_{S-H} band³ near ~ 2400 – $2600 cm^{-1}$.

The $\sim 3350 cm^{-1}$ ligand band disappears in all the complexes probably due to the formation of a phenolate ion during complex formation. It is further substantiated by blue-shift of phenolate ν_{C-O} by 10 – $20 cm^{-1}$. Further, the red-shift of $\nu_{C=O}$ band by 10 – $20 cm^{-1}$ indicates the coordination of carbonyl oxygen to the metal ion. The sharp band at $\sim 3220 cm^{-1}$ remains unaltered but the band at

$\sim 3100 cm^{-1}$ disappears thereby implying that NH group of $C_6H_5-CO-NH-CS$ moiety is involved in enolization or thioenolization in alkaline medium during complexation. The latter process seems more feasible because of the red-shift of thioamide band region by 200 – $220 cm^{-1}$ due to conversion of $C=S$ to $C-S$. A sharp band at $3480 cm^{-1}$ in all the aquo-complexes may be assigned to ν_{OH} of coordinated water molecules³ as evident from the thermal analysis. Besides, additional bands appear at ~ 580 – 520 ($M-O$), 485 – 450 ($M-N$) and 315 – $310 cm^{-1}$ ($M-S$)⁴. Thus the ligand behaves as a dibasic tridentate donor coordinating through deprotonated SH, phenolic OH and carbonyl oxygen. Steric factor prevents coordination of these ligands to the same metal ion, therefore, it acts as bridging unit by simultaneously coordinating to two metal centers probably through sulfur atom as indicated by the large shift in ν_{C-S} of $C-S$ bands.

The presence of pyridine (picolines) in coordination sphere is indicated by the disappearance of ν_{OH} band as observed in the aquo-complexes and appearance of band at ~ 1580 , 1440 and $640 cm^{-1}$ assignable to anti-symmetric ring stretching, symmetric ring stretching and in-plane ring deformation mode of coordinated pyridine (picolines)⁵.

The complexes $[M_2(BPT)_2(H_2O)_4]$ followed the same thermal decomposition pattern. There is mass-loss upto 160° , indicating the absence of lattice water or water of crystallization in them. An abrupt mass-loss supported by an endothermic peak at the same temperature in DTA curve corresponding to the loss of four H_2O molecules in a single

step is observed. This indicates that the coordinated water molecules are in same chemical environment. On further heating, there is slow and regular mass-loss perhaps due to decomposition of organic moiety in the complexes. Finally, the curve attains stability in the range 500° and the final residue corresponds to the formation of CuO, CoO and NiO. Thermal stability of the complexes follows the order : $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$.

Table 1. Physical data of complexes*

Compd.	Colour	% Metal : Found (Calcd.)	ΔM in Ω^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$
H ₂ BPT	Brown	-	-
[Co ₂ (BPT) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Brown	16.15 (16.18)	6.2
[Ni ₂ (BPT) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Brown	16.09 (16.10)	5.3
[Cu ₂ (BPT) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Grey	17.18 (17.22)	6.4
[Co ₂ (BPT) ₂ (Py) ₄]	Pink	12.10 (12.11)	6.5
[Ni ₂ (BPT) ₂ (Py) ₄]	Yellow	12.05 (12.09)	5.7
[Cu ₂ (BPT) ₂ (Py) ₄]	Green	12.91 (13.02)	6.3
[Co ₂ (BPT) ₂ (α -pic) ₄]	Cream	11.44 (11.47)	6.8
[Co ₂ (BPT) ₂ (β -pic) ₄]	Cream	11.44 (11.47)	6.2
[Co ₂ (BPT) ₂ (γ -pic) ₄]	Cream	11.44 (11.47)	6.1
[Ni ₂ (BPT) ₂ (α -pic) ₄]	Green	11.40 (11.42)	5.4
[Ni ₂ (BPT) ₂ (β -pic) ₄]	Green	11.40 (11.42)	5.5
[Ni ₂ (BPT) ₂ (γ -pic) ₄]	Green	11.40 (11.42)	5.2
[Cu ₂ (BPT) ₂ (α -pic) ₄]	Brown	12.22 (12.25)	6.3
[Cu ₂ (BPT) ₂ (β -pic) ₄]	Brown	12.22 (12.25)	6.8
[Cu ₂ (BPT) ₂ (γ -pic) ₄]	Brown	12.22 (12.25)	6.1

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

The electronic spectral bands of the present complexes occur only in specified positions indicating the two metal centres to be equivalent with similar geometry. The room temperature magnetic moment values of the complexes are found to be normal which rules out the possibility of metal-metal interaction.

The room temperature μ_{eff} values for the Co^{II} complexes (4.5–5.0 B.M.) suggest high-spin octahedral geometry, which is further supported by the electronic spectral data. The ligand field bands of the complex are observed at 8050–8155, 16200–16280 and 19580–20200 cm^{-1} , assignable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)(\nu_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$ transitions, respectively⁷. The values of transition ratio ν_2/ν_1 and other factors like *B*, *C*, F_2 , F_4 and β lie in the range 2.11, ~840–860 cm^{-1} , ~3900 cm^{-1} , ~1400 cm^{-1} , ~112 cm^{-1} and 0.86, respectively, providing further evidences for octahedral geometry for the Co^{II} complex.

In the Ni^{II} complexes, μ_{eff} values at room temperature

are in the range 2.98–3.38 B.M. as expected for six-coordinated spin-free Ni^{II} species. For these complexes tetragonal splitting for the excited levels ${}^3T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^3T_{1g}(F)$ has been observed. The split component for ${}^3T_{2g}(F)$ are observed near 8500 and 10800 cm^{-1} , the relative intensity of the former being higher. The split components of ${}^3T_{1g}(F)$ are located near 14000–15000 cm^{-1} , intensity of the later being higher. The two higher components of ${}^3T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^3T_{1g}(F)$ terms are assigned to E_g level which manifests that the tetragonal distortion of the octahedron is through elongation along 4-fold axis and this suggests clearly that the ligand exerts a stronger field in the chelate ring than the axial water (pyridine or picolines) molecules. Besides, there is a band at 27000 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ transition⁷. The values of distortion parameters as calculated by known methods are, D_t , D_s , D_qE , D_q^A lie in the range 184–210, 212–226, 1045–1062, 774–723 cm^{-1} , respectively. These data further support for a distorted octahedral geometry for the Ni^{II} complexes.

The Cu^{II} complexes exhibit normal magnetic moments (1.85–1.92 B.M.) as shown by d^9 -systems with one unpaired electron⁸. The data accounts for a slight orbital contribution to the spin-only value and absence of spin-spin interaction in the system. All these complexes show broad asymmetric ligand field bands in the region 15550–18125 cm^{-1} and CT band at 28220–30670 cm^{-1} . The former band may be due to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition suggesting thereby a distorted octahedral geometry for these complexes⁹.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. or G.R. grade. The solvents were purified before use. The ligand (H₂BPT) was prepared by the reported method¹⁰ by refluxing a mixture benzoyl isothiocyanate and *o*-aminophenol in dry acetone, yield 60%, m.p. 226°.

$[M_2(\text{BPT})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ ($M = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ and Ni^{II}) : To an ethanolic solution of the appropriate hydrated metal(II) chloride, ethanolic solution of ligand (H₂BPT) was added in 1 : 1 proportion and the pH was adjusted to 7.5–8.0 by adding aq. NaOH. All the complexes that precipitated out were digested on a steam-bath. The resulting solids were washed with water, ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl₂.

$[M_2(\text{BPT})_2(L)_4]$ ($M = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ and Ni^{II} and $L = \text{pyridine}$ or picolines (α, β, γ)) : To an ethanolic suspension of $[M_2(\text{BPT})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, pyridine or picoline (α, β, γ) was added dropwise under reflux till a clear solution was obtained. It was then allowed to evaporate slowly at room temperature. The residue left after evaporation of the solvent was washed

with ethanol followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl_2 .

The metal contents were determined by standard method. Sulfur was estimated as BaSO_4 . C, H, N were analyzed by semimicro combustion process. Magnetic moment was measured by Gouy method at room temperature using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant and diamagnetic corrections were made¹¹. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Spekol 2V (Carlzeia) spectrophotometer.

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